

Theil-Sen Estimation for Moran's I : A Robust Representation and Estimation Approach

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Summary

The OLS-derived local Moran estimator is extensively studied. Yet, few have focused on whether it may be possible to estimate local Moran statistics in a statistically-robust fashion. Indeed, robustness is important when trying to distinguish between *spatial outliers*, which are unusual observations relative to other observations within a geographic locale, and *distributional outliers*, which are unusual observations no matter where they are or who they're around. We show how robust Moran estimation actually involves two problems: (I) how do we robustly represent the surroundings of each site? and, (II) how do we robustly estimate the relationship between sites and their surroundings? We show that an optimally-robust estimator, the Trimmed Least Squares estimator, and the Theil-Sen estimator solve both representation and estimation issues fairly well. We posit that the Theil-Sen estimator should be explored as a default estimator for local and global Moran's I statistics.

KEYWORDS: *Spatial statistics, local Moran's I , local indicators of spatial association, robust statistics, geographic data science.*

1 Introduction

Spatial analysis often involves the detection of patterns and the identification of spatial autocorrelation, which can provide insights into the underlying processes driving spatial distributions. One of the most widely used measures for identifying local spatial autocorrelation is Local Moran's I (Anselin, 1995). The Local Moran's I statistic is a thoroughly-used spatial statistic used to summarise the local covariance of a spatial pattern around the global mean. Its most useful trait (relative to other local statistics like the Getis-Ord G (Getis and Ord, 1996)) is that it indicates both *clustering*, areas where the values being mapped are all unusually similar, and *outliers*, where an observation is quite dissimilar from its surroundings. Like many local statistics, the Local Moran's I is related to a global Moran's I (Moran, 1948), which is obtained using an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator (Cliff and Ord, 1981; Anselin, 1996). The paper introducing Local Moran's I has

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been cited over 17,000 times (Anselin, 1995), and the statistic is used thoroughly in spatial analysis beyond geography.

While the development of Moran’s I was occurring, a parallel trend of work in the 1980s focused on estimation of *robust* linear regression (Theil, 1950; Sen, 1968; Rousseeuw et al., 1987). In this literature, the main concern is that OLS line-fitting techniques are highly sensitive to outliers or skew. Indeed, the concept of the *breakdown point* is used to explain how sensitive techniques are to outliers. Presaging modern adversarial machine learning frameworks, the *breakdown point* of an estimator measures how much of the data can be corrupted or mis-encoded before the estimate itself is changed arbitrarily far from its original value. While OLS regression estimators can be defeated with a single point (and thus have a breakdown point of $1/n$), the Trimmed Least Squares estimator can achieve the theoretical highest breakdown point (50%) while other common estimators (such as the Theil-Sen estimator) still achieve quite high breakdown points ($\approx 30\%$). From this body of work, a very large portion of thoroughly-used statistics have been developed or adapted (Rousseeuw et al., 1987), especially for situations where robust line-fitting must occur within a larger machine intelligence pipeline; these techniques provide an integrated solution to identifying a trend while isolating the influence of outliers.

As this literature emerged alongside the nascent local revolution (Fotheringham, 1997), it was not thoroughly integrated within the spatial statistical literature.¹ For instance, Getis (1999) and Unwin and Unwin (1998)’s review of contemporary techniques during the period of rapid local statistical focus exclusively on Moran, Geary, and Getis-Ord statistics. One effective exploration of robust spatial statistics (Sen and Sööt, 1977) was largely missed by this nascent local statistical literature, while contemporary work on autocorrelation statistics typically focus on new functional forms of the statistic (Lee, 2001; Li et al., 2007; Griffith, 2010; Wolf, 2024) or structural assumptions about its use (Sauer et al., 2021; Westerholt, 2022). Thus, while we have a vast diversity of local statistical approaches, each has its own hyper-specialized niche of usage.

Since each of these new statistics is basically defined in the manner it is estimated, it’s often the case that an estimator and the *estimand*, or the conceptual quantity the estimator is trying to recover, are seen as identical. Yet, this need not be the case. As Li et al. (2007) note, the choice of Moran-form regression is itself a specification decision about what local spatial autocorrelation will mean; different choices about the functional form of the statistic will change what how such autocorrelation is represented and thus change the estimand. Therefore, one might wonder why we use an estimator with such a low breakdown point as OLS to estimate the Moran-family estimand—an estimator that can be easily *mislead* by outliers should probably not be used to *identify* outliers.

This problem can be visualized easily in Figure 1, where the same spatial pattern goes from indicating a significant number of high-high clusters to mainly low-low clusters as we increase the skew of the distribution. Note too that in central London, some hotspots change to spatial outliers due to the increasing skew.² As this example shows, the very low breakdown point of the global Moran’s I is inherited by its local components. In a similar fashion, an outlier located *strategically* could

¹A story the authors have seen before (Zhang and Wolf, 2024).

²While skew is formally distinct from the concept of an outlier, this example induces skew by simply increasing the highest observation’s value relative to the others. Thus, skew here increases as outliers in one tail increase in severity.

Figure 1: The same relative spatial pattern with different levels of skewness. Note that the visual pattern remains the same, but stretching out the tail of the distribution shifts the bulk of High-High clusters (visualized in red) into Low-Low clusters (visualized in blue).

adjust local statistics simply by its appearance in z_i or $\sum_j w_{ij}z_j$. However, a single outlying observation located *anywhere* can still shift local statistics *everywhere* through the global mean, changing hotspots into cold spots or outliers. Thus, we need more robust estimators for this purpose.

2 Thinking Through Robust Moran Statistics

We show how the Trimmed Least Squares (TLS) and Theil-Sen estimators provide two useful yet distinct frameworks for estimating robust global and local Moran’s I statistics. Before this, however, it is important to understand how Moran estimators have traditionally been analyzed. As Anselin (1996) argues, a Moran estimator can be derived from a line-fitting procedure on the Moran scatterplot. Local estimators, as Anselin (1995) notes, can be thought of as influence or outlier statistics relative to this line. The local Moran statistic is a regression-derived statistic, which is obtained from the following regression structure:

$$\mathbf{W}z = \alpha + Iz + e$$

where \mathbf{W} is the spatial weight matrix, z is the deviation from the mean, and e represents random noise. The global I statistic is obtained from the least squares estimator of the slope from this regression:

$$\hat{I} = (z'z)^{-1}z'\mathbf{W}z = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \sum_j z_i w_{ij} z_j \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of observations. And local statistics switch the “inner” product to an “elementwise” one (Wolf, 2024):

$$I_i \propto (z'z)^{-1}z' \circ \mathbf{W}z \tag{2}$$

This means Moran’s I is the least squares estimator of the line of best fit in a Moran Scatterplot (Anselin, 1996). It is also a (scaled) average of the local I statistics, a necessary property of any Local Indicator of Spatial Association (Anselin, 1995).

When thinking about a robust form of this statistic, two questions are important to answer: (I) how can we robustly measure the surroundings of each site? and then (II) how can we robustly estimate the relationship between this measure and the site values? The former addresses the impact of outlying z on the measure of context, while the latter addresses the impact of these outliers on the calculation of local association. Using OLS with the local median x solves (I), not (II) (Nardelli and Arbia, 2024). Even if we then estimate the model using a robust estimator (solving II), the overall robustness the second estimation step is *conditional upon* the robustness of the representation step.

Instead, it is possible to come up with an integrated solution, addressing both steps within the same approach. We outline two ways this can be done. First, the *trimmed least squares (TLS)* estimator uses the trimmed spatial lag within a TLS to solve (I) and (II) simultaneously. Second, the Theil-Sen regressor uses medians and a pairwise estimator to address both together.

2.1 Trimmed Least Squares Estimates for Moran’s I

The TLS estimator can attain the highest breakdown point, 50%. This estimator selects values of α, β to minimize the sum of the smallest p percent of squared errors. Solving the TLS problem for general y and \mathbf{X} to optimality is a combinatorial optimization problem, requiring us to find the $(1 - p)\%$ observations whose least squares estimate has the lowest error. Solving this problem for Moran-form regression is more complex, since the trimmed spatial lag must be re-calculated each time an observation enters or exits the trimmed set. It is beyond the scope of this abstract to fully specify and solve the TLS Moran integer program.

For the purposes of this abstract, we use a simpler iterative approximation that is usually sufficient to identify a decent univariate TLS Moran solution if a good initial guess (α_0, β_0) is clear. For this approximation, we set α_0, β_0 to some starting guess³ and calculate residuals $r = \mathbf{W}z - (\alpha_0 + \beta_0 * z)$. Then, we sort r^2 and drop the largest p percent of them, and sum the retained values as the *trimmed loss*. We iteratively adjust $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}$ to minimize this trimmed loss, such that pairs of observations may change from “trimmed” to “retained” at each iteration. In each iteration, for each trimmed observation, we set its column of \mathbf{W} to zero and unit-standardize by row. This ensures that trimmed observations are ignored when calculating the spatial lag—providing a *trimmed spatial lag* operator.

³This algorithm tends to fail when setting α_0, β_0 to the full-sample OLS estimates (see Rousseeuw and Van Driessen, 2006). In applied cases, outlying values of z are much more common than those in $\mathbf{W}z$, which usually reduces the slope estimate. Hence, large β_0 (like .8) and $\alpha_0 = 0$ have been successful in test problems.

At the end of this fitting procedure, we have np “trimmed” observations with large residuals and $n(1-p)$ retained with small residuals. We also obtain the final trimmed \mathbf{W}^* . Trimmed observations are set aside as distributional outliers and do not enter into the calculation of the lag for local statistics, $z \circ \mathbf{W}^* z$. Axes of the TLS scatterplot are drawn at the trimmed mean and $\hat{\alpha}$, remaining points are labelled as clusters/outliers with respect to these values, and trimmed points are labelled as distributional outliers. Permutation tests for the local statistics work in the same fashion as that for the classical local Moran statistics, except trimmed observations should be omitted from the set of candidates during shuffling.

As we show later, this works well in practice. It answers (I) representation using the trimmed local mean for robust lag calculation, and (II) estimation using a trimmed least squares estimate for robust global I calculation. However, this feels inelegant due to the new free parameter (p) which must be defined in advance. Unfortunately, while we can often find small values of p that yield nearly the same results as the severe $p = .5$, this strongly depends on the data. While $p = .5$ yields the highest breakpoint estimator, no analyst would accept throwing away half the data as distributional outliers in order to seek spatial patterns in the remaining half. Indeed, trimmed points may not themselves be *spatial* outliers and may even form the core of a cluster region.

2.2 A Strategy for Robust Estimation with Robust Representation

Instead, the Theil-Sen estimator answers both the representation question (I) and the estimation question (II) without introducing new hyperparameters. To motivate the Theil-Sen Moran estimator, it is first helpful to re-specify the Moran-form regression as a *weighted least squares regression* over all pairs of observations, z_i, z_j using weights w_{ij} . To develop this idea mathematically, let’s define Z^i and Z^j as two matched vectors of z , where each k th element describes a pair of observations. Then, let us define $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}$ to be a weights matrix of shape n^2 , where $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_{k,k} = \mathbf{W}_{ij}$. For this specification, the weighted least squares estimator is:

$$\hat{I}_{WLS} = (Z^{i'} \tilde{\mathbf{W}} Z^i)^{-1} Z^{i'} \tilde{\mathbf{W}} Z^j \quad (3)$$

This takes the same value as the standard Moran’s I formula in Equation (1) if \mathbf{W} is row-standardized. This works because the two approaches are unbiased estimators of the same estimand: the relationship between y_i and all other y_j , weighted by w_{ij} . The classical Moran estimator simply takes the (weighted) average of for all i first, and then runs OLS using this average. In contrast, the weighted all pairs regression will consider all pairs of z_i, z_j , but listen more to those with stronger weight when determining the weighted average slope.⁴

To see this in practice, consider the scatterplots in Figure 2.2. In the middle, we have the classical Moran Scatterplot, showing the relationship between z and the lag of z for a synthetic skewed variate. We can visually see that the global Moran estimate is off the mark. The slope defined by the broad mass of points is pulled downwards by the distributional outliers below the line. On the right, we see the same black Moran-style points as well as the underlying observations that *go into*

⁴For a similar non-spatial argument, see Gelman et al. (2020, Chapter 8)

Figure 2: Two ways to think about the Moran Scatterplot. On the left pane, we can see the *aspatial* distribution of z is quite skewed. The red line indicates the average, while the blue line indicates the median. This skew affects the middle facet’s Moran Scatterplot, where the black dots show z and its spatial lag and the slope of the red line corresponds to the Moran’s I value. Distributional outliers artificially lower our estimate of global autocorrelation here. However, two of these outliers would be considered *clusters* in a classical Moran analysis. On the right, we see the all-pairs plot, with the grey underlaid points representing each z_i, z_j pair that are involved in calculating the lag.

the spatial lag calculation. At any point on the horizontal axis, the vertical position of each black point is the weighted average of the grey points. Thus, the OLS estimator for Moran’s I only sees the middle plot.

This opens up an interesting angle of investigation. Conceptually, the all-pairs regression provides a more fruitful space in which to work here, since it does not depend on the robustness of the *pre-defined* summary of z_j near z_i . That is, it does not require we solve the representation problem (I) before the estimation problem (II)—we can do both at once.

2.2.1 Introducing the Theil-Sen Moran Estimator

The standard Theil-Sen estimator is one of the most common nonparametric robust regression techniques. For a simple linear regression, this estimator works as follows:

1. Consider a centered variate x , and another centered variate y .
2. Construct the set of all pairs $\mathcal{A} = (x_i, y_i), \mathcal{B} = (x_j, y_j)$ for all pairs $i \neq j$.
3. For each pair, compute the slope of the line connecting \mathcal{A} to \mathcal{B} as $(y_j - y_i)/(x_j - x_i)$
4. For all these pairs’ slopes, use the median slope as the slope estimate.

Adapting this estimator for the Moran case, we regress Z^j on Z^i using the Theil-Sen estimator, weighting each pair’s slope by w_{ij} .⁵ With this, we can obtain local and global Theil-Sen Moran

⁵We can think the weighted median as a weighted quantile function, $q(p)$ such that for percentile p , the weighted

statistics as follows:

1. Consider a centered variate z and a spatial weights matrix \mathbf{W} .
2. Construct the set of all pairs $\mathcal{A} = (z_i, z_j)$, $\mathcal{B} = (z_k, z_l)$.
3. For each pair p , calculate the slope of the line connecting \mathcal{A} to \mathcal{B} as $s_p = (z_l - z_j)/(z_k - z_i)$ and the weight as $w_p = w_{ij}w_{kl}$.
4. Calculate the weighted median of slopes s_p that start at i using w_p as weights. This is the *Local Theil-Sen Moran's I_i* .
5. Calculate weighted median of slopes s_p using w_p as weights. This is the *global Theil-Sen Moran's I* .

The global Theil-Sen Moran estimator calculates slopes between all pairs of points in the all-pairs scatterplot in Figure 2.2 and takes the spatially-weighted median. Thinking about this all-pairs set of slopes can be confusing, so let's break it down. First, note that each vertical band of points reflects the full distribution of (z_i, z_j) pairs for each site i . That is, the vertical band contains the full information to summarise a relationship between a site and its surroundings. Now, imagine z_i is below the mean, and has many neighbors much larger than it. In the all-pairs scatterplot, these points would lie in the upper left; all other points at z_i would have $w_{ij} = 0$. Then, we can think about the lines connecting points (z_i, z_j) to points at some site (e.g., k). If z_k is large and its neighbors are small, then the values with $w_{kl} > 0$ are in the bottom right. If we connect a point at random at $(z_i, *)$ to a point at random in $(z_k, *)$, the slope will be negative when both $w_{kl} > 0$ and $w_{ij} > 0$. If many k are like this, then the relationship between z_i and nearby z_j tends to be dissimilar from the relationship between other z_k and other nearby z_l .

Once the global and local Theil-Sen Moran estimates are obtained, cluster classifications are immediately available from the median of z and the Theil-Sen intercept:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \text{median}_{ij} |Z_j - \hat{I}_{TS} Z_i, w_{ij}| \quad (4)$$

The median z and $\hat{\alpha}$ define a classification strategy for each site. A hotspot (coldspot) is where z_i is above (below) median z and the locally-weighted median is above (below) $\hat{\alpha}$. Spatial outliers reflect cases where z_i is on the opposite side of the median as the locally-weighted median for i is from $\hat{\alpha}$. Permutation inference can be applied similarly to the typical local Moran case.

3 Example

In this example, we simulate fifty points uniformly at random in the unit square and use their Thiessen polygons as a spatial support. We draw Lognormal(0, 2) variates and filter these using a simultaneous autoregressive structure with $\rho = .75$:

quantile value $q(p)$ measures the smallest sample value z_k that is greater than at least p percent of the total sample weight. In this case, the weighted median is simply $q(.5)$, measuring the sample value z that splits the sorted sample into two equally-weighted halves.

Figure 3: Global estimates for three Moran estimators, alongside the underlying all-pairs scatterplot. In the all-pairs scatterplot, darker points have larger w_{ij}

$$y = (I - .75\mathbf{W})^{-1}\text{Lognormal}(0, 2)$$

A realization of this process was shown earlier in Figure 2.2, in the top left pane, and its spatial distribution is shown in Figure 3. This distribution is highly skewed, and has clear outliers in z , as well as outliers in joint $z, \mathbf{W}z$. It is also highly structured spatially. Its global Moran’s I estimate is statistically significant at .45, while about a quarter of the local I_i estimates have p -values below .01. We can see visually in both Figures 3 and 3 that the global Moran estimator is clearly failing to address the outlying observations. The estimated slope is too conservative—patterning in the map is *higher* than the distributional outliers would lead one to believe. One can see a main sequence of points and the distributional outliers in the lower right visually, but the OLS estimator splits the difference. The Theil-Sen estimator does a better job of recovering the global slope and ignoring the outliers. The 8% trimmed least squares estimator is shown in dashed green in Figure 3. Here, $p = 5\%$. This corresponds to two observations identified as outlying, shown with dark black outlines in Figure 3.

4 Conclusion

Robust statistics are useful and important methods when setting “defaults” for the statistical analysis of data. Things like heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors and local kernel regressions are ubiquitous in exploratory data analysis, as the Moran-family spatial statistics are in geographic

Figure 4: Example map showing two robust Moran estimator results, alongside the OLS estimators and original map.

data analysis. At its core, however, Moran statistics are built around two assumptions: that (I) the representation of a site’s surroundings is well-represented by the local average, and (II) that the ordinary least squares slope is a good estimate of the relationship between sites and surroundings. This is a very strong assumption to make for an exploratory statistic used to detect outliers. When distributional outliers exist, both global and local Moran statistics can take on counter-intuitive values. This is because neither representation nor estimation decisions are robust for classical Moran’s I . This paper outlines how Theil-Sen and Trimmed Least Squares estimators can address both in a rigorous way. Because it does not introduce a new hyperparameter, we suggest that the Theil-Sen estimator can become a robust default for both global and local Moran-style statistics in the future.

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